

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20810522

The Problems Of Broken Homes On Academic Performance Of Secondary School Students In Damaturu Metropolitan Council, Yobe State

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ABSTRACT

This survey research conducted to find out the problems of broken homes on the academic performance of secondary school students in Damaturu metropolitan council of Yobe state. Two objectives and three research questions were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study consists of the junior and senior students in four selected secondary school in Damaturu metropolitan council. Through the process of simple random sampling a total number of 800 students were selected to participate in the study. The major instrument used for collecting data was a questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed through the use of simple percentages. It was discovered based on the analysis that most of the respondents are not staying with their parent. They performed below expectation due to lack of security, care and discipline. Their school fees are not being paid in time. On the basis of such findings, recommendation were made that, Yobe state government should create academic and counsel unit in secondary school with adequate funds, where students from broken homes would be given proper guidance and counseling concerning their psychological and social problem.

Keywords: academic performance, broken homes, secondary school students,

INTRODUCTION

Broken home occurs as a result of separation of marriage either by death or divorce. Broken home contributed a lot to anti-social behaviour society. Isake (1963) stated that most of them were very unsuccessful because of separation of house; he said broken house can be as a result of divorce of separation by death of the couple.

The problem of broken homes are universal phenomenal which affect both developed as well as the under developed countries. Yet the courses and effect still persist with varying degrees in the various part of the world. In an ideal atmosphere, Children should happily be with their parents, children appreciates the love

of their parents towards them, one of the tasks that should be fulfilled by parents, is to educate their children because the education of children does not start from school. This is because live schooling of students started from home. A home is the walls of the house but the people who live on it make a home. A house only becomes a home, when it is complete. A home also became a house when is not broken. Hemm (1970), Maintained that; broken home means a heroic in which the parents are separated or divorced or are no more by either as a result of death. Children from such home lack proper care and security. The suffering of such children could be seen in differed dimension. In most cases, adequate parental and affection may not be given to the children properly by the adopted parents, that is the guardian. The death of the parents may be as a result of wars, suicide, murder etc. leading the children losing their parents. Unfortunately for the children who find themselves in such a manner can be neglected by the fear groups and society instead of being love and care for the present day in Nigeria. The rates of broken homes are increasing unprecedented, consequently and it is necessary for the psychologist and teachers to find out the relationship between houses and academic performance of the concern children.

Parent (1970); homes are a dwelling place. This author went on to say that it is also a place of natural shelter from rain, sun and cold which is the season. The other point he stressed on was security and care while its concluded by the fact that it provide a place for happy family life with room and equipment for preparing and eating means for recreation. When a student imagines his home a "Vacuum Can" Which exposes him or her to same problems in the environment. In some societies in Nigeria and other Parents in Africa, such children are regarded as neglected. Isake et al (1984), mothers are considered as the backbones or major providers of programme of services to individual children. Based on the needs and understanding of his environment, they said children from broken home feel very sad when they lack the carrying, affection, security and concern for lovely home. Such children tend to develop a kind of inferiority complex, and aggression, hostility, reserved and isolated among their pear groups. When children are not secured and not enjoying the love and parental upbringing, it will affect the cognitive loved of the children, thereby affecting their academic performance.

However, as the home became as insecurity, place, the children are respond by developing tension, prostration and aggression and broken home could causes the children to feel isolation and humpies. Yusuf (1981) revealed that 60 – 70% of backward students of secondary Schools are those children from broken homes; some of them are rerunning errant, while some of them do not have adequate school material that will help them to study. Hence, there are frustrated and psychologically disturbed, when they are in classroom as a result they cannot do well in the school activities.

Statement of the problem

The statement of the problem is therefore stated thus, to what limit do broken homes causes by separation divorce or death of parents affect children or student academic performance.

- a) The children social life will be affected because they do not have time for the rest when parents are not available.
- b) Dropping out of the school: children from broken homes tend to dropped out from school, because of no body to cater for their need.
- c) Malnourishment, sick, sleeping, hunger: these can also affect children from broken homes, due to inadequate balance diet and other vices.
- d) Domestic services: domestic services like sweeping, washing etc. can also deprive them from doing assignment, home work etc.
- e) Truancy: the children from broken home tend to be trounced because, they have feeding of dislike of school and other activities.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:-

1. To determine whether actually broken homes has an effect on student's academic performance.
2. To determine the number of students from broken home in the selected secondary schools in Damaturu Metropolitan council.
3. To advice parents who have such children to do something about their condition.

Research questions

- a) Does lack of parental discipline affect student's academic performance?
- b) Does lack of parental care, affection and love affect student academic performance in secondary schools?
- c) Does lack of Parental security affect student's general activities?

Significance of the study

Many people do not see broken homes as a social problem, which affect children born into such homes.

- i. The study aims to some extent see how this affects children in their academic performance.
- ii. The study will not only be restricted to Damaturu Metropolitan only, but Yobe State in general and also the country at large.
- iii. The study will also advice parents who have such children to think of their future, and those who can assist them to do something for them.
- iv. The study will be an effective tool in the hands of guidance and counseling personnel's and also psychologist to suggest way out.
- v. The study would also be relevant to teachers in order to help their students despite the problem in the study.
- vi. It will also attempt to some extent suggested some hopeful advice and counseling to people who may like to apply them to their marital life situation.

RELATED LITERATURE

The reviews of the related literature are examined under the following subheadings:

- i. Theoretical frame work and nature of broken home.
- ii. Broken homes and academic performance.
- iii. Implication of divorce on academics Performance.
- iv. Broken homes implication to teachers in School setting.
- v. Summary and Uniqueness of the study.

The Theoretical Framework and Nature of Broken Home.

According to Ghaerba (2001) broken home is situation whereby the family is engulfed with his understanding of marriage and family structure. This implies mal adjustment, mal functioning psychological decadents and the existence of family squabbles. Akintayo (2002) referred to single parents family as a broken home she describe single family condition where either the man, woman takes care of children alone without the help of the second party or parties, Akintayo explain further that single family have become permanent and noticeable features in many societies today throughout the world. According to Homeby (1970), broken home is a home in which the parents are separated due to divorced or are not living together as a result of death.

Lovell (1973) opened that families spites by death, desertion, and divorce or prolong absence. In assessing the above definition such as a situation (broken home can result to poor academic performance in primary schools as once child misses such opportunities of guide, securities affection and assistant where necessary. Janet (2002), a single parent mother of three stated that; in Hung Kong, where old chines values are still strong, the divorce rate is more than doubled in six years between 1981-2987. In Singapore divorce among both Muslims and non Muslims increased almost 70 percent between 1980 - 1988.

According to Gharba (2001) in this study identified reasons for broken home under various type of family disorganization as follows:

A divorce cause:

- A. Maltreatment from man
- B. Lack of proper care for the family
- C. Maladaptive behaviour by other party
- D. Charge of adultery
- E. Charge of witchcraft against wife
- F. Broken home due to death of bread winner

- i. Husband
 - ii. Wife
- G. Marriage without mutual consent**
- i. Husband dislike wife
 - ii. Lack of true love
 - iii. Wife dislike husband
 - iv. Parental disagreement
- H. Separation case caused by**
- i. Economic activities (Trading)
 - ii. Problem of urbanization
 - iii. Quest for job (social mobility)
 - iv. Economic inequality
 - v. Breakdown of social status
- I. Inter family misunderstanding**
- i. Childlessness
 - ii. Disrespect and disloyalty
 - iii. Interference from both parties family members
 - iv. Inability to have desire to have sex especially male children is another to have broken homes. Broken home have been known to be due to poverty misunderstanding between couples, external interference of in-law, adultery love for material, wealth instead of love for husband and wife especially in urban areas, childlessness, or sterility, love for money, guest for getting marriage or anybody that comes ones way due to other age or likes, prolong illness and insanity for the disability such as blindness, paralysis or illness caused by accident.

Research shows there is a tendency for product of broken home to more likely experience the problems later in marriage. Girls married from a broken home have high tendency to end up in the same way, because they have been trained not to belong to single man throughout their life time. Children from broken home are affected educationally, hence the focus on Damaturu metropolitan council students. It is known that the home is the school of children and is the place where foundation of life service is laid. The children from broken home are easily moved emotionally than their counterparts stable homes Gharba (2001).

Broken Homes And Its Relationship To Academic Performance.

Wallerain and Kelly (2004) stated that the absence of father is often viewed as partially harmful to self esteem looking at the above critically one will be correct to say that a child that has no self esteem will not be able to perform well in his academic work and as such one will not be able to perform well in school. Ezewu *et al* (2000) have noted that if the child from broken homes fails to make necessary adjustment at school, he becomes mal-adjusted and this might make him resort to any of these course actions. He may attempt to change the situation violently and as a student he would see both teachers and seniors as threat to his existence in the school and would attack them.

According to Banjo (2000) the home influences the child at the most impressionable time of his life, at a time when his mind is most receptive it provide the first impression on while of the child's subsequent life. It is home that child learns his earliest lesson in obedience, politeness and the school work in the same direction. If the home and school work in the same direction towards the best development of the child, the result will be most happy, if the school pulls in the same direction while the home in another, the child true development is bound to be handicapped it's true that a family or broken cannot be conductive for the smooth learning of the child in that, the home will only succeed in pulling done what has been learnt by the child in the school because of lack of reinforcement from the home. A more have been investigated into the relationships between broken homes and academic performance. DUCAN (1973) started that the relationship between home variable and academic performance are positive but the broken home has made it negative.

However, the existence of this negative relationship between broken home and academic performance cannot generally tell us very much of the nature of the casual relationship, that exist between the variables. Further investigation and understandings of parents have no time for them; they indulge in bad behaviour like fishing, stealing and alcoholism etc.

Fosukun (1954), argued that serious conflict will be arises between the home and the school with this category of children lack motivation, the parent are unable or refused to provide the basis needs of the children, subsequently their academic performance will be adversely affected. Nell (1981), the students may in approximately one of this situation. In the first instance, the student may find himself being brought up in a single parental family there is likely to be increased financial hardships. During time parental illness there may be few additional social resources to call upon.

All these will mean in the school, the student may have to withdraw due to nonpayment of school fees or in cases when he is not withdraw. He may not be able to catch up with his mates. Rohner et al (1975) states that body contact most important requirement for the infant attachment to wrath has adverse effect on intelligence and the creativity of the student to them, a student from such a home will face a problem of learning, disability he is aggressive and unable to obey school rules.

Implication of Divorce on Student Academic Performance.

Liman (2012) stated that, divorce is the final termination of marital union, concealing the legal duties and responsibility of marriage and dissolving the bends of matrimony between the parties. In other word, divorce is defined as a dissolution contract between a man and a woman by the judgment of a court of competent jurisdiction or by an act of legislature. Liman (2012) adultery, infertility, dissertation, negligence, abusive treatment and infidelity are reason for divorce. There are many implication of divorce on the academic performance secondary school students. Geoge (2000) opened that the implication of divorce on the academic performance of children, especially in examination and continuous assessments, pose a great problem in our society. Unstable parents must bear in mind that children's education is pivot on which their lives depend, and considered to be the most vital avenue for promoting worthwhile children. Failure to maintain a stable unity and give the children sound education will hamper their progress in life, growth and development and even the society in general.

It is not doubt that children from divorced family perform poorly in academic as a result of emotional instability and coordinated direction life. Akinboye (1992) maintain that during the confusion period of family and high emotional intensity in divorce families, anti-social action occurs more frequently among children of divorce than other groups. Thus, this behaviour materializes as fighting bullying on other children, cheating, lying and stealing which affects their cognitive and perception academic performance. Oniboken (2005) states that a poorly arranged visitation schedule, aggravated by different transition schedule, aggravated by different transition between the parents home may prevent a child from functioning well in school. A single parent may also have difficulty in coping with raising a family while working at the same time. Parents need to remember that divorce is stressful for the children, just as is for the parents. Frude (1981), shows that when a children from broken homes are compared with children from intact marriages the alter are better adjusted and have better relationship with parents. But when another crucial comparison was made between children from broken home forced better in every comparison less delinquent behaviour better adjustment to parent when the adolescents from intact but unhappy homes. For children the absence of emotional supports on effective role model agent of socialization, trainer or skills disciplinarian and better agent.

However, in marriage where the father has been distant, uninvolved and non supportive, there may be little to lose and much to gain from opportunities for new relationship, self sufficiency and relief from conflict. From the evidence available it can no longer be maintained that divorce is entirely detrimental to children. It may be said that marital conflict and disruptions are disturbing to children and disorganized their lives. If divorce removed the sources of conflict then divorce is better for the children than living in conflict. In the case of death being a casual factor of broken home, the situation appears to be different from that of the father pact in fostering the student.

Broken Home Implication to the Teacher in School Setting

The section take into consideration Broken Homes and its implications for the teacher and the student's performance even when the school situation are different the problems are common phenomenon such as broken homes problems that are from the parents and not from the school situation that affect the student environment. Bliss (2004) states that broken homes are often different for the teachers to overcome in the absence of vital feedback he has about each student through the teachers need to know the general problems children from broken home are likely encounter such problems include frustration, insecurity, anxiety, and emotional block. It is generally believe that individuals exposed to such problems mentioned have the difficulties of organizing themselves and to concentrate to do any school work properly.

In a divorce situation the attitude of the parents would consent seriously on whether their children would perform well or fail to perform well. For example for some individual will fail to strive in a confused and tense atmosphere. If separation occurred and the students is in the custody of the parents preferred his school work will not be seriously disturbed. Wodton (1959) reported that in the field delinquency, especially delinquent girls the evident supporting the view broken homes play an important role, which involved emotional in strong and consistent. There are form of broken home which has emotional and stresses, but merely students from broken homes, are emotionally disturbed which lead to badly affected in their academic performance. Children who were reported with emotionally disturbed in a researched conducted by Yusuf (1981) revealed that about 272 children or 32% of them came from broken homes obviously a relationship exist between broken home and the emotionally disturbed among are common. School administration can lead the way in reassessing attitude policies a programme that affect families involved in divorce transition. By emphasizing high expectation. By and a positive school environment and by providing support to mobilize students strengths.

METHODOLOGY

This section of the research deals mainly with the methodology or strategies in which the researchers used in collecting valid and reliable information and data for the study, which includes:

- a. Research design
- b. Area of study
- c. Population of the study
- d. sample and sampling Procedure
- e. instrument for Data collection
- f. Procedure for data collection
- g. Method of data analysis

Research design

The research is a survey design on the effect of broken homes on academic performance of secondary school students in Damaturu Metropolitan council. Ndagi (1984), survey research is a type of descriptive research in which respondents for testing hypothesis concerning the states of some educational problem are measures. It is also techniques involving larger number of persons and described population characterized by the selected of unbiased sample. It involved using questionnaire and sometimes interview test and generalizing the result of the survey to the population from which it's drawn.

Area of Study

This Research was conducted within Damaturu Metropolitan council. Damaturu is a Local Government area of Yobe State, Nigeria its headquarter are in the town of Damaturu, the state capital, the postal code of the area is 620, the local government area has an area of 2,366km² and a population of 88,014at the 2006 census. The town of Damaturu is on A3 highway and has an estimated 2010 population of 44,268. Damaturu is the headquarter of the Damaturu Emir, at one time part of the Ngazargamu Emir based. The north easterly line of equal latitude and longitude passess through yhe area including 12⁰⁰00¹⁰⁰"N 12⁰⁰00¹⁰⁰"E / 12.00000⁰N 12.00000⁰E in the north.

Population of the study

The populations of this research consist of the senior and junior students in the four (4) selected secondary schools in Damaturu Metropolitan council. Two hundred (200) respondents per school have been randomly selected.

Sample and sampling procedure

Random sampling was adhering, thereby bringing the total number of respondents. Eight hundred (800) participated in the study.

Instrument for data collection

The instrument used in collecting data for this study is a questionnaire, which was constructed by the researchers under the supervision of the supervisor. The structured questionnaires were design and adhere throughout the study. The method used in analyzing the data collected was given to the respondent to provide supplementary importation where appropriate, in order to analyze the data statistically, the percentage method was used to present the data collected in which a way that it can easily be interpreted. The formula adopted was percentage formula.

The questionnaire was divided into three parts. **Part A**, deals with the personal data of the responder, **Part B**, deals with the number of students from broken homes which were randomly selected to participate in the study and **part C** deals with the problems of broken home on academic performance of the respondents.

Procedure for data collection

The items selected for the questionnaire were scrutinized typed out and printed clearly in the computer. They were distributed to two hundred (200) senior and junior students in each four – selected secondary school under Damaturu Metropolitan council. The respondents were asked to fill in the forms and return it to the researchers for analysis the researchers divided themselves into two groups. Each group visited two (2) secondary schools to save time.

The exercise was carried out within (3) days. There were a total number of 800 questionnaires distributed. The respondents were selected randomly without bias. Moreover, for the purpose of administrating the questionnaire that was first taking to the office of the secondary schools. The principals directed the teachers concerned in the schools to co-operate and feed the researchers with the necessary information refined for the study.

DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Introduction

This chapter discusses the presentation and analysis of data based on the investigation carried out on the problems of broken homes on academic performance of secondary school students with particular reference to some selected secondary schools in Damaturu metropolitan council of Yobe State. Percentages (%) were employed as the statistical tools for analyzing data. The results of the analysis are presented in percentage terms merge for “Yes or No”. The data for the research work was obtained through the questionnaires. The results are presented according to the research question raised earlier as showing in the table below:

Table 1: Number of Students and Their Percentage from Broken Homes

S/NO	Variables	YES	(%)	NO	(%)
1.	Whether mother is alive?	650	81.5	150	18.75
2.	Whether father is alive?	600	75	200	25
3.	Whether father and mother stay together?	200	25	600	75
4.	Do you stay with your parent?	200	25	600	75
5.	Do your parents love you?	130	16.25	670	83.75
6.	Do your parents care for your progress in school?	150	18.75	650	81.25

Table 4.1 above presents frequency distribution on the number of students from broken homes. 81.25% of the respondents agree that, their mothers are alive. 18.75% of the respondents agree that, their mothers

alive are not alive. 75% % of the respondents agree that, their father alive is alive. And 25% of the respondents agree that, their father is not alive. While 75% of the respondents agree that, their fathers and mothers alive are not staying together. 25% of the respondents also agree that, their fathers and mothers are staying together.75% of the respond that, they are not staying with their parents. And 25% of the % of the respondents answers that, they are not stating with their oarents.83.75% of the students respond agreed that, their parent doesn't love them, while 16.25% of the respond answer that their parents love them. 81.25% of the respondents agree that, their parents do not care for their progress in life and finally 18.75% answer that, their parents do care for their progress in live.

Table 2 Frequency Distributions on Problems of Broken Home on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students and Their Percentage

S/NO	VARIABLES	YES	(%)	NO	(%)
1.	Do you perform poorly in your home assignment because of absence of your father	650	81.25	150	18.75
2	Do you perform poorly in your test because of absence of your father or mother?	620	77.5	180	22.5
3	Do you perform poorly in your terminal exams because of absence of your father or mother?	600	75	200	25
4	Do you perform poorly in your group assignment because of absence of your father or mother?	680	80	160	20
5.	Do you perform poorly in your quiz, drama, debate because of absence of your father or mother?	620	77.5	180	22.5
6.	Does lack of security affect students from broken homes in school?	600	75	200	25

Majority of the respondent which constitutes 81.25% of the respondents agreed that they perform poorly in their home assignment because of absence of their father or mother, while 77.5% also agreed that they perform poorly in their test because of absence of their father or mother. Similarly, 75% of the respondents also agreed that they perform poorly in their terminal exams because of absence of their father or mother. 20% of the respondents disagreed that they perform poorly in their group assignment because of absence of their father or mother. Similarly 77.5% of the respondents also disagreed that they perform poorly in their quiz, drama, debate because of absence of their father or mother. Similarly, 75% of the respondents agreed that lack of security affects students from broken homes in school.

Table 3: This table Shows Frequency Distributions on Problems of Broken Home on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students and Their Percentage

S/NO	VARIABLES	YES	(%)	NO	(%)
1.	Does indiscipline affect the performance of students from broken homes?	650	81.25	150	18.75
2.	Does a student from broken homes that lack security perform below expectation?	600	75	200	25
3.	Did your parent taught of you when you come late from school?	250	31.25	55	68.75
4.	Do your parents provide you necessary security for you?	150	18.75	650	81.25
5.	Do your parents beat you when you do bad	200	25	600	75
6.	Do your parents ask the school authority to discipline you when you do wrong things	170	21.25	630	78.75

From the above table, about 81% respondents agreed that, indiscipline affect performance of students from broken homes, while 25% of the respondents disagreed that, students from broken homes, that lack security perform below expectation. And 68.75% of the respondents disagreed that, their parents are taught of them when they come late from school. Similarly, 81.25% of the respondents agreed that their parents do not provide necessary security for them. Similarly, 75% of the respondents agreed that their parents do not beat them when do badly. Finally, 78.75% of respondents disagreed that their parents ask the school authority to discipline them when they do wrong things.

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

It is evident from the first findings of this study that about 75% of the respondents are not staying with their parents. According to Hornby (1970), broken homes is a home in which the parents separated or divorced or are no more together as a result of death. Children from such homes lack proper care and security. The sixth findings indicated that 70% agreed that lack of security affects students from broken homes in schools and 90% of the respondents agreed that, students from broken homes that lack security perform below expectations. Yusuf (1999) stated that 60 – 70% of backward students in school are those children from broken homes. Some of them are rerunning errant while some others do not have adequate school materials that will help them to study hence that they are frustrated and psychologically disturbed, when they are in the classroom as a result they cannot do well in the school.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained in this research, the research concludes that,

- i. Most of the respondents are not staying with their parents.
- ii. They perform below expectation due to the, lack of security care and discipline in school.
- iii. The study further concluded that, some of the factors which causes psychological effects on students academic performance as a result of broken home, are lack of ;
 - a. Care security and discipline.
 - b. Lack of awareness from religious scholars lead to the problems of broken home.
 - c. Most of the respondents perform poorly in their quiz and debates.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that:-

- a) The government should create academic and counseling units in schools with adequate found, while students from broken homes should be given proper guidance and counseling concerning their psychological needs and social problems towards their studies for appropriate discipline.
- b) More learning materials should be provided to the students from broken homes by their parents and guidance for effective learning
- c) Proper monitoring, security and discipline should be given to the students by their guidance and single parents.
- d) Government should found or create sufficient orphanage homes and finance them, so that they will take care of broken homes.
- e) Religious scholars should offer to parents on dangers of broken homes and their effect on academic performance.
- f) Principal and teachers should monitor the affairs of students from broken homes and counsel them from time to time in their schools.

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